

Tacit knowledge Significantly boosts the decision - Making process

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Abstract – Modern age is an age of cut throat competition. It is very difficult to become a successful businessman in the modern age. We know very well that success in any business depends upon knowledge and the decision- making process. Knowledge is the main power. It is a valuable asset of any organisation or institution. In this research Paper we will discuss about tacit knowledge and how it boosts the decision making process. The decision making process is an intellectual Process which plays Vital role in development in any organisation. Tacit Knowledge is a hidden knowledge which can be acquired through experience, insight, Observation and meditation. Tacit knowledge was introduced by Michael Polanyi in the year 1958 in his book ' personal knowledge. Tacit Knowledge and decision making process is the main part of human resource Management. all managerial activity revolves around the decision Process. Tacit knowledge Is an intangible asset. It cannot be expressed easily. It can be passed on only by example. Tacit knowledge can be defined as skills, ideas and experiences. Tacit knowledge is accessible and how it plays an integral role in the context of strategic decision making. I hope that better decision making will occur when Tacit knowledge is applied at the time of decision making. Tacit knowledge is used in different areas as like health sector, education, business, industry or organisation strong Tacit knowledge sharing is vital for creating inviting solution. lastly, we can say that Tacit knowledge, can be applied in any sector and I hope that tremendous progress can be made certainly.

Keywords - to analyse different types of knowledge, features of Tacit knowledge, to analyse decision-making process, Tacit knowledge and how it boosts the decision- making process.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern age is an age of cut throat competition. In the modern era, each and every business faces many challenges and I know very well that success of business depends on knowledge and the decision making process. Main purpose of this research paper is to analyse the needs and importance of Tacit Knowledge and how helpful it is in the decision making process. We will also analyse the relation between Tacit knowledge and the decision making process, Tacit knowledge plays a significant role in development of any organisation. Our analysis demonstrates that Tacit Knowledge is a component of the decision making process.

Knowledge is the main power which plays a vital role in the development of any organisation. knowledge is also the main part of Human resource Management. we know That knowledge best concept of them can be very useful for strategy formulation. knowledge refers to Idea or understanding with and individual process and those that are effectively utilised for achieving business goals,

Tacit Knowledge is the personal knowledge embedded in invisible experience which is shared and exchanged through direct face to face contact and in which include personal wisdom, experiences, insight and intuition etc. Tacit knowledge is practical knowledge which is obtained from experiences. Decision making process is an intellectual process which is basic to human behavior and everyone within the organisation is a decision maker of varying degree and importance. However, those who are designated as managers accept a role which specifically

emphasizes organizationally oriented decision making responsibility.

Generally, the organisation's broad decision making theories can be put in two categories;

- Normative, mathematical and economic theories
- Behaviour theory

Early theories of individual are based on assumptions central to the theory of an 'economic man' an 'economic man' is assumed to know the entire alternative available to him in a given situation and consequences of each. it is further assumed that he behaves rationally i.e. he is able to orderlies preference according to his own hierarchy of values and he always choose so as to maximize some desired values.

Tacit knowledge is the only way to take control over the decisions made in haste. Tacit knowledge brings new beliefs about many people's people. That new belief will help to make a variety of decisions whose result can be better.

Therefore, Tacit knowledge boosts the decision making process.

Main aim and objective of this study

There are the following aim and objective of this research work;

- To analyse knowledge and different types of knowledge
- To analyse Tacit knowledge
- To analyse decision-making process
- To analyse how Tacit knowledge boosts the decision-making process.

To analyse knowledge and different types of knowledge:- we know that very well knowledge is the main power of human being. Knowledge is the most crucial thing in the management of an organisation which helps in achieving the business goals. In this research paper, we will discuss Tacit knowledge and how it boosts the decision making process.

According to Webster's dictionary, knowledge is the condition of knowing something with familiarity gained through experiences of association. Knowledge refers to ideas or understanding which an individual possesses and those that are utilised effectively for goal realisation. Kinds of knowledge:- There are 2 types of knowledge

(i)Explicit knowledge/formal knowledge:-Explicit knowledge is the formal knowledge which can be obtained from reports, articles, manuals, patent pictures, videos and images etc. in other words, we can define explicit knowledge as the knowledge that can be easily shared, documented and is often stored in a tangible form such as a manual, database or report.

Tacit knowledge/implicit knowledge:-Tacit knowledge is such type of knowledge which is obtained from experiences, insight and intuition. At first, Tacit knowledge was introduced by scientist Michael Polanyi in the year 1958 in his book 'personal knowledge'. 'This paper mainly discusses the value of Tacit knowledge applied in decision-making. Tacit knowledge cannot be expressed easily. It can be passed on only by example from master to apprentice. Tacit knowledge can be defined as skills, ideas and experiences. 3) To analyse Tacit knowledge:- The concept of Tacit knowledge refers to knowledge that cannot be fully codified. Tacit knowledge is not easily accessible.

I hope that better decision-making will occur when Tacit knowledge is applied at the time of decision-making. sternberg also proposed that Tacit knowledge can be taught referring to his teaching classes in 'how to apply for job,how to write resume, how to do job interviews (1996 P.246)so on. Although this may appear contradictory to the definition. It is in fact congruent. These skills are practical and important in obtaining real world goals for the students. He was referring to those who wanted to get jobs when they graduate. Non- verbal acquisition of Tacit knowledge is apparent in the mentor-apprentice relationship and on-the -job training. Actually these processes can benefit any one. We focus on top level mangente remind consistent with our context of strategic decision making.

To analyze the decision-making process:- Decision-making is an intellectual process. Decision-making is such a process in which it includes recognising the problem, analyzing profit and selecting the best alternatives the option should be in maximum profit and minimum loss. Etymologically, the word 'decide' is derived from latin. Prefix de meaning 'off' and the caedo meaning to cut'.In

this sense, some cognitive process cuts off as preferred or elects a particular course of action from among a set of possible alternatives. The process of meeting and resolving a choice-making situation is decision- making. The statement so often made the decision-making the organizational activity which has resulted in plenty of literature in this field. (Bernard 1938) (Simon 1957). Such research has been of interest not only to the psychologist behavioural scientist but also to the scientist. The psychologist had come relatively late to the study of decision- making but most of the work has been carried out by investigation from other areas. A large part of his work however has been essentially normative in character. The mathematical statistician, management scientist and frequently the economist has his primary objective in the construction of a model which will tell the decision maker how he should make decisions. The economist has a descriptive as well as normative interest. Contribution to psychology is usefully summarized by edward and tversky (1967) from public administration by chapman (1968) and cyert and march (1963) attended to use interdisciplinary framework and further , economic approaches of siegel and fouraker(1960) and (1965).

In general way, the organisational decision-making theories can be put in 2 broad categories:

- Normative, mathematical and economic theories
- Behavior theories

It is the second of these two approaches that concerns the present study. The interest here is in tracing decisions rather than what is ideally expected to happen.in this connection,the work of simon(1957) and March & Simon (1958) offers the most material assistance. This research work focuses on Tacit knowledge, behavior for decision-making and also emphasizes an 'Economic man' who is assumed to decide on the basis of his perfect knowledge.

Most descriptions of decision-making emphasize the model point where choice is made. (Varoom 1964,Taylor 1965) Decision making process is used in different organisations in different ways.

To analyse how Tacit knowledge boosts the decision-making process:- This research paper demonstrates that Tacit knowledge is the key component of decision- making process. now, we are discussing how Tacit knowledge posts the decision- making process in an organisation. we know very well that success of any organisation depends upon its decision maker. it is also well known that good decision is the symbol of development of organisation. Tacit knowledge plays vital role in decision-making can accelerate knowledge management by helping employees solve problems faster,make better decisions and innovate. Recording Tacit knowledge promotes more efficiency on boarding of new recruits by providing them with valuable insights from experienced coworkers. It also helps to formulate strategy in industry.

COLLINS emphasizes the decision-making process that informs much of Tacit knowledge. In concluding,Collins

argues that most human activities require Tacit knowledge to make decision.some writers too claim that all knowledge is Tacit knowledge.

There are many examples of persons of different fields who achieved success due to Tacit knowledge.

Sir Jamsetji Nusserwanji Tata was motivated to set up an iron and steel company in India but he faced many challenges. Because of his single-mindedness and tenacity. He succeeded in establishing such enterprises after 17 years of struggles. He had an urge to create a great change in Indian business. He did not only reform Indian business but also the nation. It is a matter of boundless amazement that a child born in a priestly household, who had neither higher education nor knowledge of business would become the ' Bhismapitamah of Indian business world'.he only had sheer passion to fulfil his dreams.

Intuition:- We can explain Tacit knowledge by giving another example which is intuition. Intuition is an innate ability to understand circumstances without using logic. We can say that it is a great skill for entrepreneurs you possess because it can enable them to identify when the best time is to launch a new product.

There are numerous surveys and research reports are available on intuition where in mainly linked in surveys among Indian professional revealed that 83% Indians believe that there intuition and trusted peers more important than AI in decision making, inspite of AI further more research shows that even top leaders and hospitality professionals really on experience and feeling for significant decisions and this enhance the quality of design making.

Great leaders make smart decision even in difficult circumstances, from albert Einstein to open Winfrey many top leaders describe their success to having followed their intuition.

Now, a team of researchers from the university of new south Wales has come up with a novel technique demonstrating just how much unconscious in tuition can inform and even improve our decision making. The research team psychological. scientist Galang andeven lafityanto ,chris donkin and joel person recently published

their finding in psychological science . to measure in tuition, the research designed on experiment in which participants were exposed to emotional images outside conscious awareness as they attempt to make accurate decisions. The result of the study denote that even when people were on were of the images, they were still able to use in formation from the images to make more confident and accurate decision.

These date suggest that we can use unconscious in formation in our body or brain to help guid us through life, enable better decision, faster decision and be more confident in the decision . lastly we can say intuit plays vital role of development of every fields heath , education and public Sector or private sector.

II. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion:- After a thorough study of the above subject matter, we reached at a certain point that Tacit knowledge is a valuable resource for an industry and it must be used properly in an organisation for achieving the business goals. That person who has the Tacit knowledge himself is unaware of the fact that he needs to express and develop this knowledge for all-around development of any field can take place.

Suggestions:-

- Tacit knowledge is required to be enhanced & applied properly by every individual as it is the process of making the best possible judgement.
- It should be used in organisations to make the best possible decision as it often provides different context to problem solving and decision-making.
- Tacit knowledge should be transferred through training in organisations for innovation & can be essential for a number of reasons.
- It helps to take butter decision making and problem solving so it is applicable to apply in decision making process Lastly,I hope that tremendous progress at any business or organisation can be made certainly if the above mentioned points are implemented properly in the business.

REFERENCES

1. P. Jyothi and D,N Venkatesh Oxford University press	Human resource management Pg.438 published in 2006
2. Pattanayak, professor I.I.M indore	Human resource management Tacit knowledge
3. Knneth A.Grant	Electronic tacit knowge journal knowledge management volume 5 issue 02 2007

4. R.A.chapman	“Decision making” published by london routledge regan in 1968
5. Fremont A. Shull,Jr. Andre’ L. Delbecq,and Larry L. Cummings	“Organization Decision making” published in new york by Mc Graw Hill in 1970 (Page 29)
6. Edwards w and tversky A (EDS 1967)	“Decision making” hardmondsworth penguin book chapman R.A. 1968 Decision making London Routledg regen paul simon H.A. 1957
7. Segals Seigel and Fouraker 1960	“Bargaining and group decision making” published McGraw Hill in 1960
8. Timothy R. Amidon	“Troubling the Tacit:A review essay of harry collins’s (2010)Tacit and Explicit knowledge”published in composition forum 49, summer 2022
9. Girish kuber	“The Tatas : how a family built a business & a nation”published by Harper business in 2019, Page No. 2,18
10. https://m.economicalimes.com	
11. https://share.google/8ri6w1w2G7wwY16zh	